

The Accountability and Transparency of School Operational Assistance (BOS) Management in East Kalimantan

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 11 December 2025	This study was conducted to determine the influence of accountability and transparency on the effectiveness of School Operational Assistance (BOS) fund management, with stakeholder participation as a moderating variable. The research method used is quantitative, using statistical data to test the hypotheses. The research objects were private elementary schools (SD) and junior high schools (SMP) in East Kalimantan. The results indicate that accountability has a positive, significant effect on the effectiveness of BOS fund management, whereas transparency does not. Stakeholder participation has a negative, insignificant moderating effect on the influence of accountability on BOS fund management effectiveness. However, it provides a positive and significant moderating effect on transparency's influence on BOS fund management effectiveness.
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I. INTRODUCTION

The BOS program supports the implementation of school-based management. This concept provides flexibility in planning, managing, and supervising the program based on each school's conditions and needs. The BOS fund management process involves several parties: the principal, the school treasurer, teachers, and the school committee. These parties play an important role in ensuring the success of BOS fund management. The same applies to public and private elementary (SD) and junior high schools (SMP) receiving BOS funds in East Kutai Regency. The BOS funds received by SD students in East Kutai amount to Rp1,070,000 per student per year, while those received by SMP students amount to Rp1,310,000 per student per year. This significant amount will be wasted if not appropriately managed.

Accounting standards serve as reporting criteria to ensure public accountability. Olii et al (2021) state that effectiveness is a key factor in successful BOS fund management. Effectiveness is the achievement of objectives. It relates to the alignment between expected results and actual outcomes. Higher achievement levels indicate higher effectiveness. Several issues arise from funds being misallocated from government-defined purposes.

Transparent fund management will encourage stakeholder participation. Nuriyawati et al (2024) found that community participation in managing BOS funds can be an effective strategy for improving the quality of education. However, Agestina et al. (2023) and Putri et al. (2023) found that

parental participation had a negative, insignificant effect on BOS fund management effectiveness.

In some privately managed schools receiving BOS funds, various studies have reported consistently high fund absorption rates over several years, even when formal mechanisms for disseminating BOS financial information to stakeholders are limited. Although high absorption may suggest efficient utilization, previous research has also noted cases in which relatively large shares of BOS budgets were allocated to consumption-related expenses during school activities. Referring to Permendikbud No. 06 of 2021, article 21 on the prohibition of BOS fund usage, there is no explicit prohibition against financing consumption for school activities. Consumption expenses may be included in operational activities, but oversized spending on consumption causes concern.

This consumption budget should be reduced to reallocate funds to support school operational activities, such as facility maintenance and the procurement of multimedia equipment.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

A. Stewardship Theory

Stewardship theory holds that management focuses on organizational rather than individual goals. Management acts in accordance with collective interests. When management's interests conflict with the organisation's, it prioritises cooperation over resistance.

Loi et al (2025) state that, according to stewardship theory, there is a close relationship between organizational success and owner satisfaction. Organisational success reflects the maximised utilisation of the principal and steward groups. Stewards protect and maximise organisational wealth through performance. A key assumption of stewardship is that managers align organizational goals with the owner's objectives.

B. Stakeholder Theory

According to Mahajan et al. (2023), stakeholder theory is a theory that encourages organizations to acknowledge and consider their stakeholders. The organization must provide value to its stakeholders.

C. Effectiveness

According to Kastori (2023), effectiveness is related to the degree of success of an operation in the public sector. An activity is considered effective if it has a significant impact on the ability to provide public services in accordance with predetermined targets. The word "effective" in the Indonesian dictionary means having an impact. Effectiveness is the ability to produce results.

D. Accountability

Nurintan et al. (2025) define accountability as the obligation of the entrusted party (agent) to convey, report, disclose, and account for all its activities to the trustor (principal), who has the right and authority to demand such accountability. The purpose of accountability is to foster public trust. Syahara et al. (2024) state that accountability involves being responsible for managing resources and implementing entrusted policies to achieve predetermined objectives.

E. Transparency

Budget transparency in the education sector refers to the openness of actions and policies taken by schools in the budgeting process that concern the common interest. Transparency aims to build mutual trust between schools and the public by providing adequate information. Transparency is a mandatory aspect of the budgeting process and of reporting on the management of BOS.

In the management of BOS funds, the parties who have the right to participate are the school management and the students' parents, represented by the school committee.

F. Research Model

Figure 1. Research Conceptual Framework

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses a quantitative research approach. Quantitative methods are used to test hypotheses with accurate statistical data. The data collected are numerical. The study examines the influence of accountability and transparency on BOS fund management effectiveness, with stakeholder participation as a moderating variable.

The population consists of teachers, staff, parents, and community members around SD 1, SD 2, SD 3, and SMP. The data used are quantitative data, with primary data collected from questionnaires and secondary data from school documents and related articles.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

G. Result

The statistical findings are specific to the sampled schools and should be understood within the limits of self-reported perceptions and local administrative practices.

Table 1 Hypothesis Testing Results

Hypothesis	Original Sample	T-statistic (O/STDEVI)	P values	Result
H1 : Accountability has a significant effect on the effectiveness of BOS fund management	0,464	3,893	0,000	H1 - accepted
H2 : Transparency has a significant effect on the effectiveness of BOS fund management	-0,210	1,804	0,129	H2 - rejected
H3 : Stakeholder participation moderates the effect of accountability on the effectiveness of BOS fund management	-0,183	1,370	0,171	H3 - rejected
H4 : Stakeholder participation moderates the effect of transparency on the effectiveness of BOS fund management	0,228	1,976	0,048	H4 - accepted

- a. H1: The results show that accountability has a positive and significant effect on the effectiveness of BOS fund management. The original sample (O) value is 0.464, the T-statistic is 3.893, and the P-value is 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). This indicates that the higher the level of accountability, the higher the effectiveness of BOS fund management.
- b. H2: The results show that transparency has a negative and insignificant effect on the effectiveness of BOS fund management. The original sample (O) value is -0.210, the T-statistic is 1.519, and the P-value is 0.129 ($p > 0.05$). This means that transparency does not significantly affect the effectiveness of BOS fund management.
- c. H3: The results show that stakeholder participation has a negative and insignificant effect on moderating the influence of accountability on the effectiveness of BOS fund management. The original sample (O) value is -0.183, the T-statistic is 1.370, and the P-value is 0.171 ($p > 0.05$). This indicates that stakeholder participation

does not moderate the relationship between accountability and the effectiveness of BOS fund management.

- d. H₄: The results show that stakeholder participation has a positive and significant moderating effect on the influence of transparency on the effectiveness of BOS fund management. The original sample (O) value is 0.228, the T-statistic is 1.976, and the P-value is 0.048 ($p < 0.05$). This indicates that stakeholder participation moderates the relationship between transparency and the effectiveness of BOS fund management.

H. Discussion

I. The Influence of Accountability on the Effectiveness of BOS Fund Management

The study's results show that accountability has a positive, significant effect on the effectiveness of BOS fund management. This is evident from the original sample (O) value of 0.464, a T-statistic of 3.893, and a P-value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). These results indicate that greater accountability is associated with greater effectiveness in BOS fund management.

Accountability plays an important role in determining the effectiveness of BOS fund management. The data analysis demonstrates that accountability significantly and positively influences BOS fund management effectiveness. In the context of stakeholder theory, accountability represents a crucial component, reflecting that the BOS fund management team is responsible for its performance and actions. Meanwhile, in the context of stewardship theory, the accountability of a management team that prioritises organisational interests encourages more responsible fund management.

The accountability practices implemented by the BOS fund management team at SD 1, SD 2, SD 3, and SMP include submitting on time annual reports on BOS fund utilization to the local education office. These accountability reports contain annual summaries of BOS fund usage by activity. The management team's ability to consistently submit timely reports supports effective fund management. This shows that strong accountability contributes to the effectiveness of BOS fund management.

This finding is consistent with the study conducted by Ufairah et al. (2023), which concluded that accountability positively affects the effectiveness of BOS fund management. Accountability is necessary because effective fund management requires a commitment to provide accountability to authorized and entitled parties.

J. The Influence of Transparency on the Effectiveness of BOS Fund Management

The data analysis produced an original sample (O) value of -0.210, a T-statistic of 1.519, and a P-value of 0.129 ($p > 0.05$). The original sample value of -0.210 indicates that transparency negatively affects the effectiveness of BOS fund management. The T-statistic of 1.519, which is below the

1.96 threshold, further indicates that this effect is not significant. The P-value of 0.129, which is greater than 0.05, confirms that the hypothesis (H₂) stating that transparency has a significant and positive effect on BOS fund management effectiveness is not supported.

In the context of stakeholder theory, transparency refers to the openness of information provided by the management team to stakeholders. Such transparency is believed to build stakeholder trust in the school as the managing entity of BOS funds. Transparency is also important in stewardship theory, which views the management team as stewards responsible for using entrusted resources for organizational benefit.

However, data from the questionnaires show that BOS fund management reports at SD 1, SD 2, SD 3, and SMP are not published through any dedicated public platform. Parents and the community do not have direct access to these reports. Despite this, the absorption rate of BOS funds has consistently exceeded 90% since 2021. BOS fund reports for these schools are submitted only to the education office, the foundation's management, and the school administrators. Broader publication of these reports is considered unnecessary because providing access to too many parties may lead to excessive interference. This indicates that transparency does not significantly influence the effectiveness of BOS fund management. Increased transparency often means increased oversight and input from various parties, which may lead to overly cautious management practices and longer processing times.

Information on BOS fund usage should be provided only to stakeholders directly involved. This helps ensure that oversight and feedback are more targeted. However, according to Permendikbud RI No. 6 of 2021, Appendix 1 on reporting procedures, schools are required to publish BOS fund recapitulation information in accessible public areas, such as school notice boards.

The questionnaire results also indicate that respondents doubt whether BOS fund realisation aligns with the prepared RKAS, as they lack sufficient access to information. Greater transparency by the foundation, as mandated by regulation, could reduce stakeholder concerns regarding BOS fund management.

K. The Moderating Effect of Stakeholder Participation on the Relationship Between Accountability and BOS Fund Management Effectiveness

The results show that stakeholder participation does not significantly moderate the relationship between accountability and BOS fund management effectiveness. This is indicated by an original sample (O) value of -0.183, a T-statistic of 1.370, and a P-value of 0.171 ($p > 0.05$). The negative original sample value and the T-statistic below 1.96 indicate a non-significant moderating effect.

In stewardship theory, stakeholder participation aims to foster harmonious, mutually beneficial relationships among the BOS fund management team and other stakeholders. In stakeholder theory, active stakeholder participation is

expected to enhance the effectiveness of BOS fund management. However, the findings of this study show that stakeholder participation does not strengthen the effect of accountability on fund management effectiveness.

The accountability practices implemented by the BOS management team, particularly the timely submission of reports to the education office, are already strong enough to ensure effective fund management without requiring additional stakeholder participation.

The questionnaire responses indicate that stakeholders perceive the school committee's participation as insufficient. The committee is considered less active in contributing efforts to improve educational quality. The foundation could increase the school committee's involvement in BOS fund management, even if not directly in reporting, through other supporting roles that advance the school.

L. The Moderating Effect of Stakeholder Participation on the Relationship Between Transparency and BOS Fund Management

The study produced an original sample (O) value of 0.228, indicating that stakeholder participation positively moderates the relationship between transparency and the effectiveness of BOS fund management. The T-statistic of 1.976, which exceeds 1.96, and the P-value of 0.048 ($p < 0.05$) confirm that stakeholder participation significantly moderates this relationship.

In stakeholder theory, stakeholders have the right to contribute, making their participation essential. In stewardship theory, stakeholder involvement is expected to support harmonious collaboration. Regarding transparency, stakeholders have the right to request clear, accessible information on BOS fund management. Greater transparency enables stakeholders to understand fund management processes better.

Transparency enables constructive discussions among stakeholders. These discussions are expected to generate feedback that enhances the effectiveness of fund management. In the context of SD and SMP Y, stakeholder participation, particularly from the school committee and teachers, is considered impactful because these groups have direct interests in improving educational quality.

This result strengthens the findings of Yusra et al. (2021), who concluded that stakeholder participation significantly moderates the influence of transparency on BOS fund management effectiveness.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the research findings, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Accountability has a positive and significant impact on the effectiveness of BOS fund management. Accountability is crucial because effective fund management depends on a strong commitment to responsibility by authorised and entitled parties.

2. Transparency does not significantly impact the effectiveness of BOS fund management. Greater transparency does not necessarily lead to better results, as involving too many parties can lead to inefficiency. When too many parties are involved, the process becomes slow and complicated, ultimately decreasing the effectiveness of BOS fund management.
3. Stakeholder participation has a negative, insignificant effect on moderating the influence of accountability on the effectiveness of BOS fund management. High accountability from the management team is already sufficient to ensure effective BOS fund management, even without strong stakeholder participation.
4. Stakeholder participation has a positive and significant moderating effect on transparency's influence on the effectiveness of BOS fund management. Stakeholder participation, particularly from school committees and teachers, can enhance transparency of information, creating space for discussion that supports more effective management of BOS funds.

Overall, this study highlights the crucial role accountability plays in ensuring effective management of BOS funds. Transparency is still necessary, but should be limited to relevant parties, while stakeholder participation can help facilitate constructive discussions aimed at improving the effectiveness of BOS fund management.

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